

Original Research

Vendor Financial Strength, Project Methodology, and Performance: A Resource Perspective Insight from Ghana's Public Sector

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Abstract

In Ghana, persistent delays, cost overruns and quality deficiencies have undermined public-sector construction projects, even when contractors had a large financial capacity. Such a paradox reveals an important gap in the literature about the processes by which financial resources turn into project performance. Thus, this study seeks to fill the gap by testing the mediating role of project methodology on the vendor financial strength and construction project performance relationship. The study further examines whether project methodological competence acts as an important pathway by which vendor financial capacity affects construction project outcomes. The study found that vendor financial strength has a positive impact on both project methodology and construction project performance. Moreover, project methodology has a positive direct impact on construction project performance and partially mediates the link between vendor financial strength and construction project performance. These findings imply that vendor financial capacity does not automatically translate to effective project delivery, but its association is mediated by the quality of methodological processes followed in project implementation. From a theoretical standpoint, the research contributes to extending the resource-based view and institutional theory by further explaining project methodology as a

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dynamic capability for deploying financial resources across complex institutional contexts. Practically, the results imply that public procurement systems reflected in Ghana will do well by emphasizing methodological robustness, managerial discipline as well as governance quality in their assessments along with financial assessment criteria to enhance construction project performance.

Keywords: Financial strength, project methodology, project performance, public sector.

Introduction

The construction industry plays a vital role in Ghana's economy, contributing significantly to infrastructure development, employment generation, and overall national economic growth (Baah et al., 2022; Fei et al., 2021). In Ghana, construction activities underpin key sectors such as transportation, housing, health, and education, making effective project execution critical to sustainable development outcomes (Akomea-Frimpong et al., 2023). The performance of construction projects within the Ghanaian context is increasingly influenced by the financial strength of vendors, who play a central role in supplying materials, equipment, and specialized services throughout the project lifecycle (Agyekum et al., 2022). Given Ghana's exposure to economic volatility, inflationary pressures, and delayed payments in public projects, vendor financial strength has become essential for maintaining project continuity and minimizing disruptions (Kissi et al., 2020). According to Altermemy et al. (2023), vendor financial strength enhances construction project performance by enabling efficient resource mobilization, operational stability, and adherence to contractual commitments. Financially strong vendors are better positioned to procure quality materials, retain skilled labor, and manage cash flow fluctuations, which positively influence cost, time, and quality performance indicators (Kamal et al., 2021). Empirical evidence suggests that vendors with sound financial capacity are less likely to cause project delays or abandon contractual obligations, thereby reducing the risk of cost overruns and schedule slippages (Asiedu et al., 2017).

Beyond the availability of financial resources, the performance of construction projects is significantly influenced by the management structures that govern project execution, with a particular emphasis on project methodology (Zhang et al., 2023). Wu et al. (2020) contend that project methodologies provide structured frameworks for the planning, coordination, and control of project activities; these methodologies can assist teams in managing uncertainty and complexity, thereby enabling proactive problem-solving rather than reactive responses to emerging issues.

Cheng et al. (2021) posit that clearly delineated project methodologies facilitate communication, risk mitigation, and stakeholder consensus, which are all critical for converting vendor contributions into reliable and prompt project deliverables. Project methodologies are particularly vital in construction projects, characterized by the involvement of diverse parties, overlapping responsibilities, and interdependent tasks, to ensure consistency, transparency, and accountability across the project's duration (Fewings & Henjewe, 2019). Therefore, project methodology is best understood as a

way to organize the use and integration of vendor capabilities within the larger project system, rather than just a technical tool used on its own (Whyte & Davies, 2021).

Despite a growing body of research on vendor financial strength and construction project performance (Altermemy et al., 2023; Kamal et al., 2021), limited attention has been given to the mediating role of project methodology in this relationship. Many existing studies adopt a direct effect perspective, treating vendor financial strength as an independent predictor of project performance (Bajjou & Chafi, 2020; Heaton et al., 2023), while overlooking the project methodologies that may enable or constrain its effective deployment. This focus on direct effects creates a notable knowledge gap, as it remains unclear how project methodologies might amplify, channel, or in some instances dilute the impact of vendor financial capacity on construction project performance. Without considering project methodology as a mediating variable, prior findings may offer only a partial explanation of performance differences across projects, especially in settings where formal procedures coexist with informal practices and political pressures (Zhang et al., 2023). Addressing this gap is important for advancing theoretical understanding and refining practical decision making in construction project management, since it encourages scholars and practitioners to look beyond financial indicators and engage with the procedural and managerial realities of project delivery.

The relevance of this study is pronounced in the Ghanaian construction context, where project delays, cost overruns, and quality shortfalls persist despite the use of vendor prequalification systems and financial screening mechanisms (Asiedu & Ameyaw, 2021). While financial assessments are routinely conducted during vendor selection in Ghana, recurring project failures suggest that financial strength alone may not guarantee improved performance outcomes and may even create a false sense of security for clients who over rely on balance sheets at the expense of process capabilities (Owusu-Manu et al., 2022). The existence of limited empirical studies that examine how project methodology mediates the relationship between vendor financial strength and project performance in Ghana limits the transferability of findings from developed economies and risks underestimating the influence of local institutional dynamics, such as bureaucratic delays, political interference, and capacity constraints within client agencies (Baah et al., 2022). From a Resource-Based View (RBV) perspective, these institutional constraints heighten the importance of firm-specific capabilities in Ghana, as organizations must rely not only on financial resources but also on internal process competencies, such as project methodology, to effectively deploy resources and achieve superior performance in constrained environments (Amoah et al., 2023).

Therefore, this study examines: (1) the effect of vendor financial strength on construction project performance, (2) the effect of vendor financial strength on project methodology, (3) the effect of project methodology on construction project performance, and (4) the mediating role of project methodology in the relationship between vendor financial strength and construction project performance in Ghana.

Literature review

Theoretical Framing

The resource-based view (RBV) is used in this research to make sense of why some construction projects perform better than others, even when they operate under similar macroeconomic and regulatory conditions. RBV explains that sustainable performance advantages arise from the strategic use of distinctive organizational resources and capabilities that are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable, rather than from resource possession alone (Barney et al., 2021). In this perspective, heterogeneity in internal resources and capabilities, rather than external market forces by themselves, is viewed as a central explanation for performance differences (Iruthayasamy, 2021).

Scholars also argue that combining RBV with industrial organization insights allows a more balanced understanding of how internal capabilities interact with external industry structures, which may be especially relevant in heavily regulated and procurement driven construction markets (Nayak et al., 2023). At the same time, critical analyses suggest that RBV requires ongoing refinement to remain relevant to contemporary organizational contexts that are characterized by turbulence, institutional constraints, and complex interorganizational arrangements (Pereira & Bamel, 2021).

Within this study, RBV is used to frame vendor financial strength as a strategic resource and project methodology as a capability through which that resource is activated. Vendor financial strength is conceptualized as a critical resource that can support stability, efficiency, and continuity in construction project execution by enabling timely procurement, retention of skilled labour, and resilience in the face of payment delays or cost escalation. RBV also implies that such financial resources are unlikely to translate directly into superior construction project performance unless they are configured and deployed through appropriate organizational processes and routines (Barney et al., 2021). Project methodology in this context is treated as an organizational capability that structures planning, coordination, risk management, and monitoring, and thus appears to determine how far vendor financial strength can be converted into tangible improvements in time, cost, and quality outcomes. Examining project methodology as a mediating mechanism aligns with the RBV argument that resources must be bundled, integrated, and continually adapted through capabilities if they are to generate sustained performance advantages, particularly in public-sector construction environments where bureaucratic procedures, stakeholder pressures, and institutional constraints may otherwise dissipate their potential contribution.

Project methodology in construction

Project methodology can be understood as a deliberately structured set of principles, processes, and management practices used to achieve defined project objectives within specified time, cost, and quality parameters, rather than a purely procedural checklist (Sheikhkhoshkar et al., 2023). In practice, it covers the planning, coordination, sequencing, and control of project phases including site preparation, regulatory compliance, procurement, resource allocation, execution, and monitoring (Alaloul et al., 2023). In many construction settings, including those in sub-Saharan Africa, traditional

methodologies such as the waterfall approach still dominate because their linear and sequential structure aligns public procurement procedures (Rao et al., 2022). Although this approach may be suitable where project scopes remain relatively stable, its rigidity can limit responsiveness to design changes, funding delays, and contextual shocks that frequently arise in public construction projects in countries such as Ghana (Damoah et al., 2020). In response to growing project complexity and persistent cost and time overruns, contemporary construction management has drawn more on agile and hybrid principles, emphasizing flexibility to cope with uncertainty (Chanthuranga et al., 2023). Effective construction project methodologies also rest on capable leadership, active stakeholder collaboration, and the strategic integration of technology, materials, and human resources, which together can enhance coordination, improve risk anticipation, and support better overall performance, particularly where institutional weaknesses and delayed payments already strain project delivery (Xing et al., 2021; Luong et al., 2021). In Ghana, studies on construction performance repeatedly point to deficiencies in planning, risk management, and contract administration as key drivers of delay and cost escalation, even where contractors appear technically and financially capable (Bentyl et al., 2017). On this basis, project methodology is conceptualized as the process capability through which vendor financial strength is translated into or sometimes fails to translate into improved project performance in public construction (Amoatey & Ankrah, 2017).

Project methodology is operationalized in this study as a composite multidimensional construct comprising planning rigor, monitoring and control systems, and adaptive capacity. These dimensions jointly capture the structured and dynamic aspects of project execution, reflecting how planning, oversight, and flexibility interact to influence outcomes. Conceptualizing project methodology as a composite variable aligns with the resource-based view, which treats capabilities as bundles of coordinated processes, and dynamic capabilities theory, which emphasizes adaptability under uncertainty (Barney, 2021; Pereira & Bamel, 2021). This specification allows for a more precise assessment of how vendor financial strength is translated into project performance through distinct but interrelated methodological components.

Vendor Financial Strength

Vendor financial strength refers to the financial capacity and stability of vendors to consistently meet contractual obligations and sustain project objectives throughout the project lifecycle, even when projects encounter delays, price escalation, or administrative bottlenecks (John et al., 2022). In public construction environments such as Ghana's, where payment delays and cost fluctuations are common, vendor financial strength appears to play a critical buffering role by reducing the likelihood of supply chain disruptions, cash flow breakdowns, and operational inefficiencies that can seriously undermine project performance (Larsson & Larsson, 2020).

Assessment of vendor financial strength typically involves examining financial ratios, credit ratings, liquidity levels, and payment histories, which together provide indications of vendors' financial viability and risk exposure, although such indicators may sometimes understate the volatility faced by smaller local firms in developing-country markets (Wilson, 2022). Alongside these formal financial metrics, complementary factors including vendor reputation, technological capability, and organizational maturity further

shape vendors' capacity to fulfil project financial requirements effectively and to absorb shocks without immediately passing risk back to the client (Marzouk & Sabbah, 2021). In this sense, vendor financial strength can be seen not only as a balance-sheet attribute but also as part of a broader capability set that interacts with project methodologies and institutional conditions to influence construction project performance (Altememy et al., 2023).

Construction project performance

Construction project performance refers to the systematic evaluation of how efficiently and effectively a project achieves its predefined objectives within agreed constraints of time, cost, quality, and scope, rather than simply whether it is completed or not (Aboseif & Hanna, 2023). In the context of public-sector construction, such as Ghana's infrastructure and social projects, performance is often felt most directly in communities through delayed facilities, cost escalations that strain public budgets, or visible quality shortcomings, which makes the choice of performance criteria more than a technical exercise (Ofori, 2023).

Performance is commonly assessed using a mix of quantitative and qualitative indicators, including adherence to budget and schedule, quality of deliverables, compliance with safety standards, and stakeholder satisfaction, which together provide a more nuanced picture of project success than any single metric can offer (Ingle et al., 2022). Yet, in many developing-country settings, formal indicators may sit alongside informal expectations related to political visibility, local employment, or community benefits, which can shape how success is perceived and may at times conflict with strict time and cost targets (Rajabi et al., 2022).

The level of construction project performance is influenced by multiple interrelated factors, such as the effectiveness of project management practices, clarity and stability of project objectives, availability and timing of resources, and the wider environmental and regulatory conditions in which projects are delivered (Kerzner, 2023). In Ghana and similar contexts, recurring reports of weak planning, fragmented coordination, and regulatory bottlenecks suggest that even technically sound projects can underperform when managerial and institutional supports are inadequate, which aligns with the argument that process capabilities and governance arrangements are as critical as technical design (Frimpong et al., 2020).

Stakeholder involvement appears to play a particularly important role, since early and continuous engagement tends to enhance communication, support more informed decision making, and foster collaboration among project participants, which can improve performance outcomes when interests are carefully managed (Varajão et al., 2022). At the same time, stakeholder processes can introduce additional complexity and delay if expectations are not aligned or if participation becomes symbolic rather than genuinely influential, a tension that is especially visible in public projects that span multiple agencies and community groups (Varajão et al., 2022).

Hypotheses Development

Vendors Financial Strength and project performance

From a RBV perspective, vendor financial strength can be conceptualized as a strategic resource that enables more reliable mobilization and deployment of inputs across the project lifecycle. In empirical work, such financial strength is associated with better cost control, schedule adherence, and overall project success, suggesting that financially sound vendors are better placed to sustain operations when projects face uncertainty and shocks (Bajjou & Chafi, 2020). Heaton et al. (2023) found that vendors with strong financial stability and positive reputations are more likely to be selected and tend to deliver improved outcomes, which may indicate that clients implicitly treat financial strength as a proxy for lower implementation risk. Complementing this, Vibhakar et al. (2023) identify liquidity and solvency ratios as critical indicators of a vendor's ability to maintain labour, materials, and equipment over time, aligning with the RBV emphasis on resource depth and durability. Castro et al. (2021) further show that project success metrics vary with vendors' financial and operational capabilities, reinforcing the idea that stronger resource endowments underpin superior performance. In line with these insights and RBV's focus on valuable and scarce resources as drivers of performance differentials, the study posits that vendors with greater financial strength are likely to contribute to improved project outcomes. Therefore, we hypothesize that *H1: There is a significant positive relationship between vendor financial strength and construction project performance.*

Vendor financial strength and project methodology

Within RBV, resource endowments shape not only what firms can do, but also which capabilities and practices they are able to build and sustain. Empirical literature suggests that vendors' financial strength is closely related to their adoption of structured and often sophisticated construction project methodologies, with implications for efficiency and risk management (Bashir et al., 2020; Sacconi et al., 2023). Studies by Abbasnejad et al. (2021) and Olanrewaju et al. (2020) indicate that financially stronger vendors are more inclined to invest in capabilities such as Building Information Modeling (BIM), which enhance coordination and reduce errors, pointing to a process through which financial resources are converted into methodological capabilities. Tran et al. (2020) similarly report that the adoption of green construction technologies is predominantly driven by financially robust firms, suggesting that resource slack facilitates experimentation with new methods and tools. In contrast, Wuni and Shen (2020) show that financial constraints hinder the implementation of modular integrated construction methods, illustrating how limited resources can prevent vendors from developing or applying higher order project capabilities. Altememy et al. (2023) further find that vendor reputation, which is often intertwined with financial capacity, influences methodology selection within supply chains, reinforcing the RBV notion that resource rich firms are better positioned to build and signal process capabilities. Taken together, these studies imply that vendor financial strength may underpin the development and use of more capable project methodologies. Accordingly, the study hypothesizes that *H2: Vendors' financial strength positively predicts construction project methodology.*

Project methodology and construction project performance

RBV emphasizes that resources generate superior performance when they are bundled and leveraged through organizational capabilities. In construction, project methodology can be viewed as such a capability because it structures planning, coordination, and control activities that channel resources toward project objectives (Al Nahyan et al., 2019). Empirical findings suggest that methodologically structured approaches significantly influence performance outcomes in terms of efficiency, cost effectiveness, quality, and stakeholder satisfaction (Chen et al., 2022). Lee et al. (2022) show that BIM based methodologies improve coordination, time management, and resource utilization, illustrating how process capabilities convert available inputs into smoother project execution. Lu et al. (2021) finds that DfMA approaches reduce rework and material waste, pointing to the cost performance benefits of well-designed methods. Mellado et al. (2020) highlight clearly specified methodologies, with explicit performance indicators and control points, help monitor and sustain project success, while Rajan and Santhosh (2021) demonstrate that agile inspired practices enhance adaptability and responsiveness in dynamic project environments. In RBV terms, project methodology appears to operate as a capability that enables organizations to harness and recombine resources more effectively. On this basis, the study proposes that *H3: Project methodology has a positive influence on construction project performance.*

Mediating role of project methodology

The combination of RBV and emerging empirical evidence suggests that resources alone are unlikely to guarantee superior outcomes; instead, capabilities mediate how resources are deployed and perceived. Studies examining vendor financial strength, methodology adoption, and project performance support this logic by showing that financially strong vendors achieve better outcomes when their resources are complemented by structured project methodologies (Wilson, 2022). Oduleye and Medon (2021) report that financially robust vendors can more readily implement methodologies that enhance planning accuracy, risk management, and operational efficiency, imply that financial strength facilitates the formation of capabilities that are themselves performance relevant. At the same time, Prebanić and Vukomanović (2023) argue that financial resources do not automatically translate into project success; without methodological frameworks to guide resource utilization and stakeholder coordination, their performance potential may be diluted. Uvarova et al. (2023) further shows that methodologies such as Lean, Agile, and digital construction practices enable vendors to turn financial capacity into measurable gains in cost, time, and quality. From an RBV standpoint, these findings are consistent with the view that project methodology functions as a dynamic capability that mediates the relationship between resource endowments and performance outcomes. The study thus advances the following hypothesis. *H4: Project methodology mediates the relationship between vendor financial strength and construction project performance.*

Conceptual framework

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework underlying this study. It presents a mediation model grounded in Resource-Based View, where there is a direct and indirect (mediating) relationship between Vendor financial strength, project methodology and

construction project performance. The direct relationships comprise: the influence of vendor financial strength on construction project performance (H1); the effect of vendor financial strength on project methodology (H2), and the effect of project methodology on construction project performance (H3). The indirect path examines the mediating role of project methodology on the relationship between vendor financial strength and construction project performance (H4).

Figure 1. The conceptual framework

Methodology

Participants and procedures

This study adopted an exploratory case study research design (Van Doreen et al., 2020), focusing on Municipal and District Assemblies (MMDAs) within Ghana's Volta Region. This research design was adopted because our study sought to cultivate comprehensive, context-specific understandings of the interplay between vendor financial capacity, project methodologies, and the overall performance of construction projects. The Volta Region was deliberately chosen as a singular case study site, given its varied administrative framework and the presence of active public infrastructure initiatives. The study's population encompassed 432 professionals which comprised consultants, engineers, procurement officers, budget officers, internal auditors, finance officers, work sub-committee chairpersons, and environmental health officers. Each official was selected from the MMDAs spread across the region. We further adopted a census sampling approach, which ensured complete coverage of all professionals in the MMDAs in the Volta Region of Ghana as it strengthened the depth and reliability of findings.

We used specific inclusion criteria to ensure participants had the necessary knowledge and experience in construction project implementation in the MMDAs within the Volta Region of Ghana. Respondents were required to meet the following inclusion criteria: (i) they must have been full-time employees of MMDAs in the Volta Region; (ii) they must

have at least two years of experience in public project planning, procurement, or implementation; and (iii) they must have been directly involved in at least one construction project within the last three years. These requirements were carefully chosen to ensure that the data collected reflected knowledgeable viewpoints based on practical experience of respondents.

Data collection was accomplished using a self-administered online questionnaire, which was distributed through Google Forms. After the data underwent screening and cleaning procedures, 320 valid responses were obtained from the initial sample of 432 individuals, resulting in a response rate of 74.1%. This rate is considered adequate for reducing non-response bias in survey research, a perspective supported by Johnson and Wislar (2012). Moreover, a post hoc statistical power analysis validated that the final sample of 320 surpassed the minimum requirement for identifying medium effect sizes in multivariate analysis, thus reinforcing the empirical findings' reliability (Faul et al., 2009). The adequacy of the 320 valid responses was evaluated using the 10-times rule for PLS-SEM, as proposed by Hair et al. (2017). Following Hair et al. (2017), the minimum sample size may be estimated using the “10-times rule,” which is based on the largest number of structural paths directed at any endogenous construct in the model. In this study, the endogenous construct (construction project performance) received two incoming paths; thus, the minimum sample required under this heuristic was 20 cases. Nevertheless, because the 10-times rule has been criticized for its imprecision and tendency to underestimate sample requirements, the adequacy of the dataset was interpreted more cautiously considering stronger PLS-SEM recommendations emphasizing power-oriented assessment. From this perspective, the final dataset of 320 usable responses was sufficient for model estimation in this study. However, since the study was conducted using a census sampling approach within MMDAs in the Volta Region, the findings should be interpreted primarily as context-specific and not automatically generalized beyond similar institutional settings.

Harman's single-factor test indicates that common method bias is unlikely to be a serious concern in this study. The first principal component explains 35.263% of the total variance, which is below the commonly accepted threshold of 50% (Kock, 2020).

The dataset analysed in this study forms part of the corresponding author Kornu's doctoral research. In line with standard scholarly practice, portions of the dataset have been utilised in related studies to examine distinct research questions and theoretical frameworks. However, each manuscript is conceptually and analytically independent, with no duplication of results, analyses, or interpretations. The present study offers a unique contribution by focusing specifically on the relationships among vendor financial strength, project methodology, and project performance. This approach ensures transparency while maintaining the originality and integrity of the current work, consistent with established publication ethics guidelines.

Table 1. Harman's test for common method bias

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.937	35.263	35.263	4.937	35.263	35.263
2	2.144	15.313	50.576	2.144	15.313	50.576
3	1.440	10.284	60.860	1.440	10.284	60.860
4	1.243	8.881	69.741	1.243	8.881	69.741
5	.771	5.505	75.246			
6	.660	4.713	79.959			
7	.539	3.853	83.813			
8	.520	3.716	87.528			
9	.412	2.941	90.470			
10	.376	2.683	93.153			
11	.284	2.025	95.179			
12	.257	1.833	97.012			
13	.227	1.624	98.636			
14	.191	1.364	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Measurement

The measurement scales were based on validated scales of previous construction management studies. Vendors' financial strength was measured using a 5-item scale based on Zhang and Chen (2022), Cheaitou et al. (2019), and Taherdoost and Brard (2019) and aligned with the Ghanaian context. Likewise, the project methodology scale comprised of seven (7) items based on studies from Padala and Maheswari (2023), Kerzner (2022) and Makahaube (2020). Further, construction project performance was measured using a 4-item scale adapted from Unegbu et al. (2022) and Assaad et al. (2020). The measures for all the variables were ranged on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). All the scales referenced are freely available in the public domain.

To achieve contextual validity, the adapted items underwent a thorough instrument refinement procedure tailored to the Ghanaian public construction sector. Initially, the preliminary items were scrutinized for linguistic precision, contextual suitability, and sector-specific applicability, with the aim of ensuring that the measures accurately represented the practicalities of procurement, contract management, and project implementation within Ghana's MMDA's.

Subsequently, cognitive interviews were performed with a select cohort of public construction professionals to evaluate item clarity, interpretability, and relevance; this process facilitated minor wording adjustments wherever ambiguity or contextual incongruence was detected. Subsequently, a pilot test was conducted with 30 respondents. This was done to assess item functionality, internal consistency, and response trends prior to the comprehensive survey deployment. These preliminary actions served to enhance

the scales' face validity, content validity, and their applicability across different contexts. The Institutional Review Board (IRB) approved this study, and all procedures followed the ethical guidelines for research involving people. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents before any data was collected. Respondents were also assured that their information would be kept confidential, that their identities would remain anonymous, and that their participation was completely voluntary.

Analysis

The analysis of structural relationships was conducted using partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) as it is suitable to explore the relationships, predictive analysis with a focus on smaller sample size, as opposed to using CB-SEM (Hair et al., 2017; Shmueli et al., 2019). The analytic process involved two consecutive steps: (1) assessment of measurement model (reliability, convergent validity and discriminant validity), and (2) evaluation of structural model which involved estimation of path coefficients, determination of R². To determine the statistical significance, a bootstrapping procedure with 5,000 subsamples was used to obtain t-values and p-values of all path coefficients. Multicollinearity was examined using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), and the acceptable multicollinearity was considered below 3.3 (Kock, 2020).

Results

Respondents profile

Results from table 2 shows that majority (77.8%) of the 320 useful responses are from males and (22.2%) females. Regarding age, 58.1% are between 25-45, indicating a substantial portion of working-age individuals in the sample. Additionally, most respondents (53.4%) held graduate degrees, indicating a well-educated group. Most of the respondents (68.1%) are married, 28.1% are single and 3.8% are divorced. Concerning the various roles, the respondents play in the district/municipal assemblies, (24.1%) are project engineers, (23.1%) are budget officers, (20%) are procurement officers, (11.3) are planning officers, project consultants (7.2%), finance officers (5.3%), work sub-committee chairmen (4.7%) and the remaining (4.4%) constitute environmental health and safety officers.

Table 2. Respondent demographics

Profile	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>Gender</i>		
Male	249	77.8
Female	71	22.2
<i>Age</i>		
25-35	72	22.5
35-45	117	36.6
45-55	88	27.5
Above 55	43	13.4
<i>Education</i>		
Undergraduate	83	25.9
Post Graduate	171	53.4
Professionals	29	9.1

Profile	Frequency	Percentage (%)
PHD	24	7.5
Others	13	4.1
<i>Marital Status</i>		
Single	90	28.1
Married	218	68.1
Divorced	12	3.8
<i>Role in District/Municipal</i>		
EH &S Officer	14	4.4
Project Engineer	77	24.1
Procurement Officer	64	20
Budget officer	74	23.1
Planning Officer	36	11.3
Project consultant	23	7.2
Work sub-committee chairman	15	4.7
Finance Officer	17	5.3

Measurement model assessment

Indicator reliability

The results presented in Table 3 demonstrate the indicator reliability (outer loadings) for three reflective constructs: Project Performance (PJP), Project Methodology (PM), and Vendors' Financial Strength (VFS). The PJP construct shows high loadings for two items (PJP2=0.937, PJP3=0.935). Two items from the PJP construct were not retained because their outer loadings were less than 0.7 (Hair et al., 2021). For PM items, five (5) out of seven (7) items were retained (0.752-0.834). Two items, PM6 and PM7, had factor loading that were less than 0.7 and were therefore not retained. For the construct VFS, out of five (5) items, three (3) of them were retained (0.817-0.907), while two (2) items (VFS4 and VFS5) were removed because they had factor loadings less than 0.7 (Hair et al., 2021). The results on indicator reliability therefore confirm that all indicators are reliable and suitable for inclusion in the measurement model, supporting the robustness and validity of the constructs for further structural analysis.

Table 3. Indicator reliability

	Project Performance	Project Methodology	Vendors Financial Strength
PJP2	0.937		
PJP3	0.935		
PM1		0.817	
PM2		0.752	
PM3		0.827	
PM4		0.816	
PM5		0.834	
VFS11			0.873
VFS5			0.907
VFS6			0.817

Internal consistency reliability

Table 4 displays the internal consistency reliability of the constructs, as assessed by Cronbach's alpha, rho_a, and rho_c. Each of these values surpasses the generally accepted benchmark of 0.70, thereby signifying substantial reliability. PJP reveals a high degree of internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.859$; rho_c = 0.934), which implies excellent construct reliability. PM also demonstrates considerable reliability ($\alpha = 0.871$; rho_c = 0.905), whereas VFS exhibits acceptable to strong reliability ($\alpha = 0.833$; rho_c = 0.900).

Table 4. Internal consistency reliability

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)
PJP	0.859	0.859	0.934
PM	0.871	0.885	0.905
VFS	0.833	0.834	0.900

Convergent validity

Table 5 displays the convergent validity findings, as assessed by Average Variance Extracted (AVE). Each construct surpasses the threshold of 0.50, thereby validating convergent validity. PJP (AVE = 0.877) exhibits exceptional variance explanation, and VFS (AVE = 0.751) also indicates robust convergent validity. PM (AVE = 0.656) meets acceptable standards, indicating sufficient shared variance across its indicators. Therefore, the findings collectively corroborate the claim that the constructs accurately reflect their underlying measurements.

Table 5. Convergent validity

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
PJP	0.877
PM	0.656
VFS	0.751

Effect size (F2)

Table 6 presents the effect size (f^2) results, which show the relative impact of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. The paths PM \rightarrow PJP ($f^2 = 0.111$) and VFS \rightarrow PJP ($f^2 = 0.060$) have small effect sizes, suggesting that they have a minor impact on project performance. In contrast, the path VFS \rightarrow PM ($f^2 = 0.157$) approaches a medium effect, indicating a stronger influence on project methodology.

Table 6. F2 (Effect size)

PM ----> PJP	0.111
VFS ----> PJP	0.060
VFS ----> PM	0.157

Discriminant validity

Table 7 displays discriminant validity, as assessed by the HTMT criterion. The HTMT values, ranging from 0.415 to 0.452, are all considerably below the suggested threshold of 0.85, thereby confirming sufficient discriminant validity across the constructs. This finding suggests that PM, PJP, and VFS are empirically distinct and assess different underlying concepts. Consequently, the results bolster the measurement model's robustness and the lack of construct overlap.

Table 8 presents discriminant validity using the Fornell–Larcker criterion. The square roots of AVE (diagonal values) for PJP (0.936), PM (0.810), and VFS (0.867) exceed their respective inter-construct correlations, confirming adequate discriminant validity. This indicates that each construct shares more variance with its indicators than with other constructs. Thus, the results demonstrate that PJP, PM, and VFS are distinct, supporting the validity of the measurement model.

Table 7. Discriminant validity using HTMT

	Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT)
PM <-> PJP	0.452
VFS <-> PJP	0.415
VFS <-> PM	0.420

Table 8. Discriminant validity using Fornell-larcker criterion

	PJP	PM	VFS
PJP	0.936		
PM	0.405	0.810	
VFS	0.352	0.369	0.867

Q2, R2 and SRMR

Table 8 presents the predictive relevance (Q^2), explanatory power (R^2), and model fit (SRMR) of the structural model. The Q^2 values for PJP (0.123) and PM (0.115) are above zero, indicating acceptable predictive relevance. Notwithstanding, the Q^2 values are small, which indicates weak predictive power. The R^2 values show that the model explains 21.1% of the variance in PJP and 13.6% in PM, suggesting weak to moderate explanatory power. The SRMR value of 0.068 falls below the recommended threshold of 0.08, indicating a good model fit.

Table 9. Summary of Q^2 , R^2 and Model fit (SRMR)

Constructs	Q^2	R^2	SRMR
PJP	0.123	0.211	0.068
PM	0.115	0.136	

Figure 2. PLS-SEM for direct and mediating effects

Results of Hypotheses Testing

Our study results in Table 10 found that a significant positive relationship exists between vendor financial strength and construction project performance among Municipal and District Assemblies in the Volta Region of Ghana ($\beta=0.234, p<0.05$). Hypothesis 1 was therefore supported. The result also indicated that a significant positive relationship exists between vendor financial strength and project methodology ($\beta=0.369, p<0.05$), thereby supporting hypothesis 2. The study also found that a significant positive relationship exists between project methodology and construction project performance ($\beta=0.318, p<0.05$). Hypothesis 3 was therefore supported. Project methodology mediated the relationship between vendor financial strength and construction project performance among municipal and district assemblies in the Volta region of Ghana ($\beta=0.117, p<0.05$). Hypothesis 4 was therefore supported. The results demonstrate that all structural paths are positive and statistically significant, with the 95% bootstrapped confidence intervals (2.5% and 97.5%), for each relationship not including zero, confirming the stability and reliability of the estimates.

Table 10. Path Coefficients for direct and mediating effects

Path Relationship	β (O)	M	SD	t-value	p-value	2.5%	97.5%
H ₁ : VFS → PJP	0.234	0.234	0.054	4.357	0.000	0.126	0.337
H ₂ : VFS → PM	0.369	0.371	0.061	6.049	0.000	0.245	0.484
H ₃ : PM → PJP	0.318	0.320	0.055	5.804	0.000	0.214	0.427
VFS → PM → PJP	0.117	0.119	0.028	4.154	0.000	0.067	0.179

Discussion

The study demonstrates a positive association between the vendor's financial strength with construction project performance and project methodology. The study also found that project methodology has a positive effect on project performance, and that project methodology is a partial mediator the relationship between vendor financial strength and project performance among MMDA's in the Volta Reigon of Ghana. Thus, while the

results do offer some theoretical support for the proposed relationships between vendor financial strength and project methodology, as well as project performance in MMDA contexts, they should not be considered strong predictors or explanations of project outcomes. Therefore, the results should be considered indicative rather than definitive. Future studies are encouraged to include other variables and contextual factors potentially improving explanatory and predictive power or adopting different modeling strategies to increase robustness.

The positive association exhibited between vendor financial strength and project performance suggests that vendors with better finances have greater capacity for project operation support, timely provision of resources, and reduced likelihood of gaps in the project delivery. This result is consistent with the previous findings of Bajjou and Chafi (2020), Castro et al. (2021), and Heaton et al. (2023), which found that improved financial stability leads to better cost control, schedule performance and overall project success. Secondly, the finding that vendor financial strength is significantly associated with project methodology also indicates that financially stable vendors have a greater tendency of adapting better and formal project methodologies. This confirms studies by Abbasnejad et al. (2021), Olanrewaju et al. (2020), and Tran et al. (2020) that financial capacity allows investment in tools including BIM and green construction methods.

The positive relationship between project methodology and project performance demonstrates that structured project methodologies significantly enhance construction outcomes. This is consistent with Chen et al. (2022), Lee et al. (2022), and Lu et al. (2021), who find that methodologies such as BIM and DfMA improve coordination, reduce errors, and enhance efficiency. Mellado et al. (2020) additionally show that the application of clearly defined methodologies improves monitoring and control, which in turn leads to better project results. The mediation analysis indicates that project methodology acts as an intermediary, enabling the conversion of vendor financial strength into improved project performance. This finding aligns with prior research by Wilson (2022), Oduleye and Medon (2021), and Prebanić and Vukomanović (2023), all of whom have demonstrated that vendor financial resources alone do not ensure superior project performance without the presence of structured project methodologies.

Theoretical implications

This finding extends the RBV by demonstrating that vendor financial strength acts as a strategic resource that directly improves project performance. This shows that the financial capacity of vendors can enhance sustained resource mobilization and continued operational resilience, which are essential for project performance. The finding also builds on the RBV by emphasizing that vendor financial strength supports project methodologies as organizational capabilities. This indicates that firms' ability to adopt structured and sophisticated processes is shaped by resource endowments. Thus, financial capacity of vendors has intrinsic value, and also serves as an instrument for building higher-order operational capabilities.

Furthermore, the research identifies project methodology as a pivotal capability within the Resource-Based View (RBV), directly impacting project performance. The study, therefore, illustrates that structured methodological processes improve coordination,

efficiency, and control. This finding corroborates capability-based extensions of RBV, underscoring the significance of resource organization and deployment in achieving superior project outcomes. Ultimately, the mediation effect refines RBV by establishing a resource–capability–performance relationship. The study thus demonstrates that financial resources indirectly influence project performance through project methodology. This highlights that capabilities function as mechanisms that convert financial resources into project outcomes, emphasizing that resource value is only realized through effective deployment via structured methodological processes.

Practical implications

The positive relationship between vendor's financial stability and project performance practically implies that MMDAs should prioritize thorough financial assessments when selecting vendors. Evaluating a vendor's liquidity, solvency, and cash flow can help identify those with the capacity to maintain operations amidst unforeseen circumstances, thus mitigating delays, budget excesses, and project interruptions, while simultaneously improving overall project delivery. Furthermore, the positive influence of vendor financial strength on project methodology suggests that procurement procedures should not only assess financial capabilities but also evaluate vendors' capacity to employ structured methodologies. Vendors with strong financial positions are more inclined to implement efficient planning, coordination, and risk management strategies, which are essential for enhancing execution quality within construction settings. Thirdly, the positive influence of project methodology on project performance highlights the need for project managers and public authorities to institutionalize standardized methodological frameworks such as BIM and performance monitoring systems. By investing in methodological training, enforcement, and continuous improvement, MMDAs can strengthen coordination, minimize mistakes, and improve cost, time, and quality outcomes in public-sector construction projects. The mediating function of project methodology highlights that financial resources alone do not guarantee superior project performance. It is imperative that MMDAs verify that financially sound vendors also possess strong methodological proficiencies. Furthermore, integrating financial evaluations with assessments of project management practices within procurement and oversight procedures can facilitate the conversion of financial resources into consistent and quantifiable project results.

Contextual implications

In the Ghanaian context, especially within MMDAs, these findings are particularly pertinent, given the ongoing issues of project delays, budgetary excesses, and quality shortcomings of construction projects. The limited financial resources of contractors, alongside the inconsistent implementation of structured methodologies, frequently hampers effective project execution. The findings indicate that improving both financial assessments and methodological adherence could lead to better construction project outcomes. Given Ghana's vulnerability to fiscal limitations, delayed public fund allocations, and institutional inefficiencies, financially sound vendors employing robust project methodologies are more likely to ensure project continuity and effectively manage associated risks. Consequently, the integration of financial capacity with methodological

precision is essential for improving construction performance within Ghana's decentralized public sector.

Conclusion and recommendations

This study demonstrates that improving construction project performance in Ghana's public sector requires a more integrated alignment of vendor financial capacity and project management practice than is typically assumed within existing procurement and oversight systems. While vendor financial strength remains a necessary condition for sustaining project execution, particularly under conditions of funding delays, inflation, and operational uncertainty, it is not, on its own, sufficient to ensure consistent improvements in cost, time, and quality performance. Rather, the findings show that financial resources yield performance benefits only when they are effectively structured and deployed through robust project methodologies. By empirically confirming the mediating role of project methodology, the study advances a more nuanced understanding of project performance as an outcome of the interaction between resources, capabilities, and institutional context, rather than a direct function of any single factor. Importantly, the results underscore the role of contextual and governance conditions in shaping these relationships. In decentralized public sector environments such as Ghana, where formal procurement rules coexist with informal practices and capacity constraints, the extent to which financially strong and methodologically capable vendors can deliver expected outcomes is contingent on institutional quality. This reinforces the need to move beyond resource-centric explanations toward more contextually grounded models of project performance.

To better harness the complementary effects of financial strength and project methodology, coordinated action is required across multiple stakeholders: First, public clients (Municipal and District Assemblies) should strengthen procurement frameworks by integrating dual evaluation criteria that explicitly assess both vendors' financial capacity and their demonstrated methodological capabilities. This includes requiring verifiable evidence of structured planning systems, risk management processes, and prior application of formal methodologies. Second, procurement officers and evaluation committees should adopt standardized and transparent assessment tools that balance financial metrics with capability-based indicators. Such tools can help reduce overreliance on lowest-cost selection practices and improve the consistency and defensibility of procurement decisions. Third, project managers and consultants should play a more active role during project execution by ensuring that vendors' financial resources are aligned with clearly defined methodological frameworks. Continuous monitoring—through site meetings, milestone reviews, and performance reporting—should be used to reinforce adherence to agreed processes. Fourth, vendors should recognize that competitiveness in public procurement increasingly depends not only on financial strength but also on methodological maturity. Strategic investment in project management systems, staff training, and process standardization can enhance both performance outcomes and reputational standing. Finally, policymakers and regulators should support these efforts by developing guidelines, capacity-building programmes, and enforcement mechanisms that embed both financial and methodological requirements into public procurement systems. Addressing institutional weaknesses—such as limited

enforcement and capacity gaps—will be critical to ensuring that resource advantages and methodological capabilities translate into sustained improvements in project delivery.

Limitations of the study

This study has several limitations. First, its cross-sectional design restricts causal inference, as relationships between financial strength, project methodology, and performance are observed at a single point in time rather than across project phases. Second, the focus on MMDA's in the Volta Region of Ghana, limits generalizability, as institutional conditions and procurement systems differ across different public sector contexts. Third, institutional voids were not directly measured but inferred, constraining precise estimation of their moderating effects. Finally, the model examines only project methodology as a mediator, whereas other capabilities, such as knowledge management, innovation, or relational coordination may also influence how resources translate into performance outcomes.

Recommendations for Future Research

This study could be extended in many ways by future researchers. Firstly, longitudinal and mixed-method designs could be deployed by future researchers to capture the time-varying nature of vendor financial resources, methodological capabilities, and performance. Second, future researchers could explicitly model institutional variables and their moderators of resource capability relationships such as regulatory quality, enforcement strength and political influence. Thirdly, comparative research across countries by future researchers would facilitate assessing generalizability and also show how different country contexts shape different project performance outcomes. Finally, future research should include mediators and moderators such as digital capability, knowledge management, and stakeholder coordination to build stronger models.

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References

- Abbasnejad, B., Nepal, M. P., Ahankoob, A., Nasirian, A., & Drogemuller, R. (2021). Building Information Modelling (BIM) adoption and implementation enablers in AEC firms: a systematic literature review. *Architectural Engineering and design management*, 17(5-6), 411-433. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17452007.2020.1793721>

- Aboseif, E., & Hanna, A. S. (2023). Defining the success status of construction projects based on quantitative performance metrics thresholds. *Journal of Management in Engineering*, 39(2), 04022073. <https://doi.org/10.1061/JMENEA.MEENG-512>
- Agyekum, K., Goodier, C., & Oppon, J. A. (2022). Key drivers for green building project financing in Ghana. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 29(8), 3023-3050. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-02-2021-0131>
- Akomea-Frimpong, I., Jin, X., Osei-Kyei, R., & Kukah, A. S. (2023). Public-private partnerships for sustainable infrastructure development in Ghana: a systematic review and recommendations. *Smart and Sustainable Built Environment*, 12(2), 237-257. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SASBE-07-2021-0111>
- Al Nahyan, M. T., Sohal, A., Hawas, Y., & Fildes, B. (2019). Communication, coordination, decision-making and knowledge-sharing: a case study in construction management. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 23(9), 1764-1781. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-08-2018-0503>
- Alaloul, W. S., Alzubi, K. M., Malkawi, A. B., Al Salaheen, M., & Musarat, M. A. (2022). Productivity monitoring in building construction projects: a systematic review. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 29(7), 2760-2785. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-03-2021-0211>
- Altememy, H. A., Ali, H. H., Kalf, H. A. I., Furaijl, H. B., Hasan, A. A., Qusai, N., ... & Thajil, K. M. (2023). The Role of Important Factors Affecting the Vendor Selection in the Construction Project Supply Chain: Moderating Role of Vender Reputation. *International Journal of Construction Supply Chain Management*, 13(1), 173-189. DOI:10.14424/ijcscm2023130110173
- Amoah, J., Jibril, A. B., Odei, M. A., Bankuoru Egala, S., Dziwornu, R., & Kwarteng, K. (2023). Deficit of digital orientation among service-based firms in an emerging economy: a resource-based view. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(1), 2152891. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2022.2152891>
- Amoatey, C. T., & Ankrah, A. N. O. (2017). Exploring critical road project delay factors in Ghana. *Journal of Facilities Management*, 15(2), 110-127. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFM-09-2016-0036>
- Asiedu, R. O., & Ameyaw, C. (2021). A system dynamics approach to conceptualise causes of cost overrun of construction projects in developing countries. *International Journal of Building Pathology and Adaptation*, 39(5), 831-851. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBPA-05-2020-0043>
- Asiedu, R. O., Adaku, E., & Owusu-Manu, D. G. (2017). Beyond the causes: Rethinking mitigating measures to avert cost and time overruns in construction projects. *Construction Innovation*, 17(3), 363-380. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CI-01-2016-0003>

- Assaad, R., El-Adaway, I. H., & Abotaleb, I. S. (2020). Predicting project performance in the construction industry. *Journal of construction engineering and management*, 146(5), 04020030. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CO.1943-7862.0001797](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0001797)
- Baah, C., Acquah, I. S. K., & Ofori, D. (2022). Exploring the influence of supply chain collaboration on supply chain visibility, stakeholder trust, environmental and financial performances: a partial least square approach. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 29(1), 172-193. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-10-2020-0519>
- Bajjou, M. S., & Chafi, A. (2020). Empirical study of schedule delay in Moroccan construction projects. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 20(7), 783-800. <https://doi/abs/10.1080/15623599.2018.1484859>
- Barney, J. B., Ketchen Jr, D. J., & Wright, M. (2021). Resource-based theory and the value creation framework. *Journal of management*, 47(7), 1936-1955. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01492063211021655>
- Bashir, I. R. A. M., Hamid, B. U. S. H. R. A., Jhanjhi, N. Z., & Humayun, M. A. M. O. O. N. A. (2020). Systematic literature review and empirical study for success factors: client and vendor perspective. *Journal of Engineering Science and Technology*, 15(4), 2781-2808.
- Bentyl, E., Nana-Addy, E., Asare, E.K., & Fokuo-Kusi, A. (2017). The level of existence and impact of cost and time overruns of building construction projects in Ghana. *Civil and Environmental Research*, 9(1), 36-46
- Castro, M. S., Bahli, B., Barcaui, A., & Figueiredo, R. (2021). Does one project success measure fit all? An empirical investigation of Brazilian projects. *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*, 14(3), 788-805. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJMPB-01-2020-0028>
- Chathuranga, S., Jayasinghe, S., Antucheviciene, J., Wickramarachchi, R., Udayanga, N., & Weerakkody, W. S. (2023). Practices driving the adoption of agile project management methodologies in the design stage of building construction projects. *Buildings*, 13(4), 1079. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13041079>
- Cheaitou, A., Larbi, R., & Al Housani, B. (2019). Decision making framework for tender evaluation and contractor selection in public organizations with risk considerations. *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, 68, 100620. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seps.2018.02.007>
- Chen, G., Chen, J., Yuan, J., Tang, Y., Xiahou, X., & Li, Q. (2022). Exploring the impact of collaboration on BIM use effectiveness: A perspective through multiple collaborative behaviors. *Journal of management in engineering*, 38(6), 04022065. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)ME.1943-5479.0001098](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)ME.1943-5479.0001098)
- Cheng, M., Liu, G., & Xu, Y. (2021). Can joint-contract functions promote PPP project sustainability performance? A moderated mediation model. *Engineering*,

Construction and Architectural Management, 28(9), 2667-2689.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-06-2020-0419>

Damoah, I. S., Ayakwah, A., Aryee, K. J., & Twum, P. (2020). The rise of PPPs in public sector affordable housing project delivery in Ghana: challenges and policy direction. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 20(6), 690-703.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15623599.2020.1763897>

Faul, F., Erdfelder, E., Buchner, A., & Lang, A. G. (2009). Statistical power analyses using G* Power 3.1: Tests for correlation and regression analyses. *Behavior research methods*, 41(4), 1149-1160.

Fei, W., Opoku, A., Agyekum, K., Oppon, J. A., Ahmed, V., Chen, C., & Lok, K. L. (2021). The critical role of the construction industry in achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs): Delivering projects for the common good. *Sustainability*, 13(16), 9112. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13169112>

Fewings, P., & Henjewe, C. (2019). *Construction project management: an integrated approach*. Routledge.

Frimpong, B. E., Sunindijo, R. Y., & Wang, C. (2020). Towards Improving Performance of the Construction Industry in Ghana: A SWOT Approach. *Civil Engineering Dimension*, 22(1): 37-46. DOI:10.9744/ced.22.1.37-46

Hair Jr, J. F., Babin, B. J., & Krey, N. (2017). Covariance-based structural equation modelling in the Journal of Advertising: Review and recommendations. *Journal of Advertising*, 46(1), 163-177. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00913367.2017.1281777>

Hair, J. F., Astrachan, C. B., Moisescu, O. I., Radomir, L., Sarstedt, M., Vaithilingam, S., & Ringle, C. M. (2021). Executing and interpreting applications of PLS-SEM: Updates for family business researchers. *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 12(3), 100392. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfbs.2020.100392>

Heaton, S., Teece, D., & Agronin, E. (2023). Dynamic capabilities and governance: An empirical investigation of financial performance of the higher education sector. *Strategic Management Journal*, 44(2), 520-548. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.3444>

Ingle, P. V., & Mahesh, G. (2022). Construction project performance areas for Indian construction projects. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 22(8), 1443-1454. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15623599.2020.1721177>

Iruthayasamy, L. (2021). The resource-based view. In *Understanding business strategy: confusion and consensus* (pp. 63-74). Singapore: Springer Singapore.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-33-6542-1_4

John, N. E., Nwaguru, P., & Williams, A. J. (2022). Assessing materials vendor selection in construction project supply chain: The relative importance index approach. *International Journal of Construction Supply Chain Management*, 12(2), 32-46. DOI: 10.14424/ijscsm120222

- Johnson, T. P., & Wislar, J. S. (2012). Response rates and nonresponse errors in surveys. *Jama*, 307(17), 1805-1806. doi:10.1001/jama.2012.3532
- Kamal, A., Azfar, R. W., Salah, B., Saleem, W., Abas, M., Khan, R., & Pruncu, C. I. (2021). Quantitative analysis of sustainable use of construction materials for supply chain integration and construction industry performance through Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). *Sustainability*, 13(2), 522. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13020522>
- Kerzner, H. (2022). *Project management metrics, KPIs, and dashboards: a guide to measuring and monitoring project performance*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Kerzner, H. (2023). *Project management metrics, KPIs, and dashboards: a guide to measuring and monitoring project performance*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Kissi, E., Adjei-Kumi, T., Twum-Ampofo, S., & Debrah, C. (2020). Identifying the latent shortcomings in achieving value for money within the Ghanaian construction industry. *Journal of Public Procurement*, 20(3), 313-330. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOPP-11-2019-0075>
- Kissi, E., Agyekum, K., Musah, L., Owusu-Manu, D. G., & Debrah, C. (2021). Linking supply chain disruptions with organisational performance of construction firms: the moderating role of innovation. *Journal of Financial Management of Property and Construction*, 26(1), 158-180. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFMPC-11-2019-0084>
- Kock, N. (2020). Harman's single factor test in PLS-SEM: Checking for common method bias. *Data Analysis Perspectives Journal*, 2(2), 1-6.
- Larsson, J., & Larsson, L. (2020). Integration, application and importance of collaboration in sustainable project management. *Sustainability*, 12(2), 585. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12020585>
- Lee, C. Y., Chong, H. Y., Tanko, B. L., & Klufallah, M. (2022). Effect between trust in communication technology and interorganizational trust in BIM-enabled projects. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 148(8), 04022059. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CO.1943-7862.0002299](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0002299)
- Lu, W., Tan, T., Xu, J., Wang, J., Chen, K., Gao, S., & Xue, F. (2021). Design for manufacture and assembly (DfMA) in construction: The old and the new. *Architectural Engineering and Design Management*, 17(1-2), 77-91. <https://doi/abs/10.1080/17452007.2020.1768505>
- Luong, D. L., Tran, D. H., & Nguyen, P. T. (2021). Optimizing multi-mode time-cost-quality trade-off of construction project using opposition multiple objective difference evolution. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 21(3), 271-283. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15623599.2018.1526630>
- Makahaube, J. S. (2020). *Performance measure methodology of project management practices in local government agencies*. The University of Texas at El Paso.

- Marzouk, M., & Sabbah, M. (2021). AHP-TOPSIS social sustainability approach for selecting supplier in construction supply chain. *Cleaner environmental systems*, 2, 100034. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cesys.2021.100034>
- Mellado, F., Lou, E. C., & Becerra, C. L. C. (2020). Synthesising performance in the construction industry: An analysis of performance indicators to promote project improvement. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 27(2), 579-608. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ecam-09-2018-0419>
- Nayak, B., Bhattacharyya, S. S., & Krishnamoorthy, B. (2023). Integrating the dialectic perspectives of resource-based view and industrial organization theory for competitive advantage—a review and research agenda. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 38(3), 656-679. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBIM-06-2021-0306>
- Oduleye, T. E., & Medon, J. J. (2021). A Data-Driven Cost Management Model for Improving Strategic Financial Planning and Performance Evaluation. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation*, 2(6), 524-537.
- Ofori, G. (2023). Get construction project performance parameters right to attain sustainable development goals. *Sustainability*, 15(18), 13360. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151813360>
- Olanrewaju, O. I., Chileshe, N., Babarinde, S. A., & Sandanayake, M. (2020). Investigating the barriers to building information modeling (BIM) implementation within the Nigerian construction industry. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 27(10), 2931-2958. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-01-2020-0042>
- Owusu-Manu, D. G., Alfa, D., Edwards, D. J., Roberts, C., & Thwala, D. W. (2022). Mitigating factors of financial distress causalities of project performance in Ghana. *Journal of Infrastructure Systems*, 28(3), 05022004. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)IS.1943-555X.0000698](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)IS.1943-555X.0000698)
- Padala, S. S., & Maheswari, J. U. (2023). Modeling a construction project in a matrix-based framework for managing requirement changes. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 23(14), 2369-2390. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15623599.2022.2059739>
- Pereira, V., & Bamel, U. (2021). Extending the resource and knowledge-based view: A critical analysis into its theoretical evolution and future research directions. *Journal of Business Research*, 132, 557-570. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.04.021>
- Prebanić, K. R., & Vukomanović, M. (2023). Exploring stakeholder engagement process as the success factor for infrastructure projects. *Buildings*, 13(7), 1785. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13071785>

- Rajabi, S., El-Sayegh, S., & Romdhane, L. (2022). Identification and assessment of sustainability performance indicators for construction projects. *Environmental and Sustainability Indicators*, 15, 100193.
- Rajan, E. R., & Santhosh, V. A. (2021). Adoption of agile methodology for improving IT project performance. *Serbian Journal of Management*, 16(2), 301-320
- Rao, A. S., Radanovic, M., Liu, Y., Hu, S., Fang, Y., Khoshelham, K., ... & Ngo, T. (2022). Real-time monitoring of construction sites: Sensors, methods, and applications. *Automation in construction*, 136, 104099.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2021.104099>
- Saccani, N., Bressanelli, G., & Visintin, F. (2023). Circular supply chain orchestration to overcome Circular Economy challenges: An empirical investigation in the textile and fashion industries. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 35, 469-482. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.11.020>
- Sheikhhoshkar, M., Bril El-Haouzi, H., Aubry, A., & Hamzeh, F. (2023). Functionality as a key concept for integrated project planning and scheduling methods. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 149(7), 04023053.
<https://doi.org/10.1061/JCEMD4.COENG-13427>
- Shmueli, G., Sarstedt, M., Hair, J. F., Cheah, J. H., Ting, H., Vaithilingam, S., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). Predictive model assessment in PLS-SEM: guidelines for using PLSpredict. *European journal of marketing*, 53(11), 2322-2347.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/EJM-02-2019-0189>
- Taherdoost, H., & Brard, A. (2019). Analyzing the process of supplier selection criteria and methods. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 32, 1024-1034.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2019.02.317>
- Tran, Q., Nazir, S., Nguyen, T. H., Ho, N. K., Dinh, T. H., Nguyen, V. P., ... & Kieu, T. S. (2020). Empirical examination of factors influencing the adoption of green building technologies: The perspective of construction developers in developing economies. *Sustainability*, 12(19), 8067. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12198067>
- Unegbu, H. C. O., Yawas, D. S., & Dan-Asabe, B. (2022). An investigation of the relationship between project performance measures and project management practices of construction projects for the construction industry in Nigeria. *Journal of King Saud University-Engineering Sciences*, 34(4), 240-249.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksues.2020.10.001>
- Uvarova, S. S., Orlov, A. K., & Kankhva, V. S. (2023). Ensuring efficient implementation of lean construction projects using building information modeling. *Buildings*, 13(3), 770. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13030770>
- Varajão, J., Lourenço, J. C., & Gomes, J. (2022). Models and methods for information systems project success evaluation—A review and directions for research. *Heliyon*, 8(12). DOI:10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11977

- van Dooren, E., Boshuizen, E., van Merriënboer, J., Asselbergs, T., & van Dorst, M. (2020). Making the design process in design education explicit: Two exploratory case studies. *Design and Technology Education: An International Journal*, 25(1), 13-34. <https://doi.org/10.24377/DTEIJ.article1273>
- Vibhakar, N. N., Tripathi, K. K., Johari, S., & Jha, K. N. (2023). Identification of significant financial performance indicators for the Indian construction companies. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 23(1), 13-23. <https://doi/abs/10.1080/15623599.2020.1844856>
- Whyte, J., & Davies, A. (2021). Reframing systems integration: A process perspective on projects. *Project management journal*, 52(3), 237-249. <https://doi.org/10.1177/8756972821992246>
- Wilson, E. A. (2022). *Relationship Between Vendor/Client Complementarity, Vendor Technology Maturity, Vendor Financial Stability, and It Outsourcing Project Outcomes*. Walden University.
- Wu, G., Li, H., Wu, C., & Hu, Z. (2020). How different strengths of ties impact project performance in megaprojects: The mediating role of trust. *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*, 13(4), 889-912. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJMPB-09-2019-0220>
- Wuni, I. Y., & Shen, G. Q. (2020). Barriers to the adoption of modular integrated construction: Systematic review and meta-analysis, integrated conceptual framework, and strategies. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 249, 119347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119347>
- Xing, W., Hao, J. L., Qian, L., Tam, V. W., & Sikora, K. S. (2021). Implementing lean construction techniques and management methods in Chinese projects: A case study in Suzhou, China. *Journal of cleaner production*, 286, 124944. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124944>
- Zhang, H. M., Chong, H. Y., Zeng, Y., & Zhang, W. (2023). The effective mediating role of stakeholder management in the relationship between BIM implementation and project performance. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 30(6), 2503-2522. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-04-2020-0225>
- Zhang, Y., & Chen, Q. (2022). Identifying Key Influential Factors of Bid Evaluation in Government Public Project Green Procurement in China Using BP-DEMATEL Model. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2022(1), 8223757. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/8223757>

APPENDIX

Section A: Biodata of Respondents

1. Gender a) Male b) Female
2. Age a) 25-35 years b) 36-45 years c) 46-55 years d) Above 55 years
3. Marital status a) Single b) Married c) Divorced
4. What is your role in this district/municipal? a) EH & S officer b) Project engineer c) Budget officer d) Planning officer e) Project consultant f) Work subcommittee chairman g) Finance officer
5. Highest level of education a) Undergraduate b) Post graduate c) Professionals d) PhD e) Others

Section B: Questionnaire

	Project methodology	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
		1	2	3	4	5
PM1	The processes and procedures of project objectives are clearly defined	1	2	3	4	5
PM2	Responsibility and roles are clearly defined by bidders	1	2	3	4	5
PM3	There is availability of material resources for implementing construction projects	1	2	3	4	5
PM4	Project personnel are trained and adequately resourced	1	2	3	4	5
PM5	There is sufficient demonstration of project permit approval	1	2	3	4	5
PM6	Clear rules and procedures are adhered to appropriately	1	2	3	4	5
PM7	There is an effective use of technology in the project implementation efforts.	1	2	3	4	5
	Vendor Financial Strength	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree

		1	2	3	4	5
VFS1	The vendor's financial stability was evident throughout the project duration	1	2	3	4	5
VFS2	Accurate audited account documents are provided by the bidders	1	2	3	4	5
VFS3	The vendor's financial resources were adequate to meet project requirements	1	2	3	4	5
VFS4	There is reasonable cost-risk allocation strategy provided	1	2	3	4	5
VFS5	There are alternative guarantees available for mitigating project risk.	1	2	3	4	5
	Construction Project Performance	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
		1	2	3	4	5
PP1	Construction projects in MMDAs in the Volta Region are completed on time	1	2	3	4	5
PP2	Construction projects in MMDAs in the Volta Region are completed within cost schedules	1	2	3	4	5
PP3	Quality information is provided on construction materials and verified	1	2	3	4	5
PP4	Final project outcomes meet user acceptance criteria	1	2	3	4	5

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<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Kornu, R. K., Dzansi, D. Y. and Atiase, V. Y. (2026). Vendor Financial Strength, Project Methodology, and Performance: A Resource Perspective Insight from Ghana's Public Sector. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 13(5), 531-560. doi: 10.22034/ijmae.2026.570025.1920</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_243158.html</p>	A square QR code located in the bottom right corner of the table, which likely links to the article's online version.